

Preparation of Newer Fused Benzimidazoles

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2-Aminobenzimidazole is an important nitrogen heterocyclic, a useful building block for the synthesis of a wide variety of substituted benzimidazoles¹. The 5-benzoyl derivative of 2-aminobenzimidazole is conveniently obtained either by condensation of cyanogen bromide with 3,4-diaminobenzophenone² or by alkaline hydrolysis of the widely known anthelmintic Mebendazole³.

In the present work, 2-amino-5-benzoylbenzimidazole (1) has been prepared by acid hydrolysis of Mebendazole (2). Compound 1 on condensation with acetylacetone and benzoyl isothiocyanate gave unreported fused benzimidazoles, i.e. 7(8)-benzoyl derivatives (3 and 4) of 2,4-dimethylpyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole⁴ and 4-phenyl-1,3,5-triazino[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-2(1*H*)-thione⁵ respectively. The direction of cyclisation, i.e. the position of attachment of the benzoyl group (C-7 or C-8) could not be determined from the available data.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are not corrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, mass

spectra on a Shimadzu QP 1000 spectrometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM 390 instrument. The purity of the compound was checked by tlc.

(2-Amino-1*H*-benzimidazol-5-yl)phenylmethanone (1) : 5-Benzoyl-1*H*-benzimidazol-2-yl)carbamic acid methyl ester (2; 25 g) was refluxed for 3 h with 70% H₂SO₄ (150 ml). The sulphate salt of 1 that precipitated was filtered and washed with water. The precipitate was then suspended in water (500 ml), basified with NH₄OH and set aside for about 2 h. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from 25% aqueous ethanol containing activated charcoal, (81%), m.p. 198° (lit.³ 193°) (Found : N, 17.66. C₁₄H₁₁N₃O calcd. for : N, 17.71%); ν_{\max} 3448, 3180–2120, 1680, 1160–1155, 760, 718 and 692 cm⁻¹.

(2,4-Dimethylpyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazol-7(8)-yl)phenylmethanone (3) : A mixture of 2-amino-5-benzoylbenzimidazole (1.0 g) and acetylacetone (3 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and diluted with methanol (10 ml). The resulting solid was washed with cold methanol, dried and crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals (82%), m.p. 270° (Found : N, 13.85. C₁₉H₁₅N₃O calcd. for : N, 13.94%); ν_{\max} 3050 (weak, C–H of CH₃), 1655 (benzoyl C=O), 1620, 1605, 1560 and 1520 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 301 (*M*⁺, 93.6%), 300 (*M*⁺–H, 100%), 224 (*M*⁺–C₆H₅, 83.0%), 196 (*M*⁺–COC₆H₅, 10.6%), 105 (H₅C₆CO⁺, 4.3%), 78 (C₆H₆⁺, 2.1%) and 77 (C₆H₅⁺, 2.1%); δ (CDCl₃) 2.21 (6H, s, CH₃), 6.97 (1H, s, hetero CH) and 7.48 (8H, complex multiplet, ArH).

7(8)-Benzoyl-4-phenyl-1,3,5-triazino[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole-2(1*H*)-thione (4) : To acetone (10 ml) was added ammonium thiocyanate (0.761 g, 0.010 mol) followed by gradual addition of benzoyl chloride

(1.160 ml, 0.010 mol) with vigorous stirring. The mixture was then refluxed for 0.5 h. It was cooled and to it was added 2-amino-5-benzoylbenzimidazole (2.373 g, 0.010 mol) suspended in acetone (25 ml). The mixture was then refluxed for 8 h, then cooled. The resulting precipitate was stirred with H₂O (50 ml) and filtered again to remove inorganic salts. It was then washed with water followed by acetone and crystallised from methanol containing activated charcoal, (52%), m.p. 243° (Found : N, 14.69. C₂₂H₁₄N₄OS calcd. for : N, 14.65%); ν_{\max} 3 000 (br, N-H...N), 1 660 (benzoyl C=O) and 1240 cm⁻¹ (C=S); m/z 382 (M^+ , 100%), 383 ($M+1$, 22.2%), 384 ($M+2$, 6.4%), 305 ($M^+-C_6H_5$, 93.6%), 306 ($M+1-C_6H_5$, 24.1%), 307 ($M+2-C_6H_5$, 3.1%), 277 ($M^+-COC_6H_5$, 6.4%), 245 ($M^+-HNCS-Ph-H$, 40.4%), 105 (H₅C₆CO⁺, 34.0%), 77 (C₆H₅⁺, 36.2%)

and 76 (C₆H₄⁺, 49.0%); δ (CDCl₃) 3.10 (1H, br, NH) and 7.41 (13H, complex multiplet, ArH).

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